

ClairCity: Citizen-led air pollution reduction in cities

D3.6 Environmental Justice and Air Pollution

February 2020

Document Details

Authors	Enda Hayes (UWE) Jo Barnes (UWE)
Contact	Enda.Hayes@uwe.ac.uk Jo.Barnes@uwe.ac.uk
Creation Date	09/12/2019
Date of Last Revision	28/02/2020
Description	This document seeks to explore environmental justice related to air pollution across the ClairCity case study cities and regions. The report contains a review of relevant literature on environmental justice and, where suitable data is available, an assessment of the ClairCity spatial data on air quality emissions, concentrations and indicators of socio-economic status. The primary aim is to assess the degree to which those citizens subjected to the worst impacts of air pollution are themselves responsible for the greatest emissions. The secondary aim is to explore the technical feasibility of undertaking environment justice studies at the city scale and provide recommendations for other cities.

Version History

Version	Updated By	Date	Changes / Comments
V1	Enda Hayes	09/12/2019	Initial structure and document outline
V2	Enda Hayes & Jo Barnes	14/01/2020	Inclusion of literature review and methodology outline.
V3	Enda Hayes & Jo Barnes	22/01/2020	Inclusion of first case study data
V4	Enda Hayes & Jo Barnes	12/02/2020	Inclusion of area-weighted and population-weighted case study data
V5	Enda Hayes & Jo Barnes	18/02/2020	Draft discussion and conclusions
V6	Jim Longhurst (UWE)	22/02/2020	Review of report
V7	Enda Hayes & Jo Barnes	28/02/2020	Final edits

Contributions and Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the following people for their important contributions used in the preparation of this final document and deliverable.

Quality Assurance	James Longhurst (UWE)
Native Language Check	James Longhurst (UWE)
Project internal comments and acknowledgements	The authors would like to acknowledge the ClairCity partners especially those within the data modelling teams for the generation of the spatial air quality emissions and concentrations data. Additionally, the authors would like to acknowledge the city partners for provision of suitable socio-economic spatial data for the case studies (where available) and their help in seeking it (where it was not).

Table of Contents

Document Details	2
Version History	2
Contributions and Acknowledgements	3
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Approach and objectives	10
2 Environmental Justice and Air Pollution	11
2.1 What is Environmental Justice?	11
2.2 Air pollution, health and socio-economic status	12
2.3 Qualitative assessment of the links between air pollution and socio-economic status 13	
2.3.1 European Policy	13
2.3.2 Understanding relationships at differing spatial scales of impact	14
2.3.3 Consider the relationship when developing interventions	16
3 Methodology and Data Sources	18
3.1 Spatial air pollution emission and concentration data	18
3.1.1 Overarching approach	18
3.1.2 Air Quality Emissions Data	19
3.1.3 Air Quality Concentration Data	19
3.2 Spatial socio-economic status data	20
3.3 Area-weighted spatial analysis	21
3.4 Population-weighted analysis	22
3.5 Study Limitations	22

4	Relationships between air quality emissions, concentrations and socio-economic status.	24
4.1	Bristol, United Kingdom.....	24
4.1.1	Area-weighted spatial analysis (Bristol).....	24
4.1.2	Bivariate maps (Bristol).....	27
4.1.3	Population-weighted analysis (Bristol).....	28
4.2	Amsterdam, The Netherlands.....	29
4.2.1	Area-weighted spatial analysis (Amsterdam).....	29
4.2.2	Bivariate maps (Amsterdam).....	32
4.2.3	Population-weighted analysis (Amsterdam).....	33
4.3	Aveiro Region, Portugal.....	34
4.3.1	Area-weighted spatial analysis (Aveiro).....	34
4.3.2	Bivariate Maps (Aveiro).....	36
4.3.3	Population-weighted analysis (Aveiro).....	38
4.4	Liguria Region, Italy.....	39
4.4.1	Area-weighted spatial analysis (Liguria).....	39
4.4.2	Bivariate Maps (Liguria).....	41
4.4.3	Population-weighted analysis (Liguria).....	43
5	Conclusions and Recommendations.....	44
6	References.....	46
7	Annex 1: Data Sources.....	49
8	Annex 2: Overview of the ClairCity Process.....	52

List of Figures

Figure 1: Associations between exposure to air pollutants and indicators of social vulnerability across Europe15

Figure 2: Spatial analysis process21

Figure 3: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol25

Figure 4: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol.....26

Figure 5: Bivariate map of NO₂ (left), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol27

Figure 6: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam.....30

Figure 7: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam31

Figure 8: Bivariate map of NO₂ (left), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam.....32

Figure 9: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro.....35

Figure 10: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro.....35

Figure 11: Bivariate map of NO₂ (left), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro.....37

Figure 12: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident population unemployed for Liguria40

Figure 13: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against resident population unemployed for Liguria40

Figure 14: Bivariate map of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident population unemployed for Liguria42

Figure 15: ClairCity process including key phases and activities (Environmental Justice Assessment highlighted in red box)54

List of Tables

Table 1: Spearman's rank correlation of Index Multiple Deprivation and concentrations/emissions in Bristol.....26

Table 2: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Bristol28

Table 3: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of households in low-income band and concentrations/emissions in Amsterdam29

Table 4: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Amsterdam ..33

Table 5: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of resident individuals without economic activity and concentrations/emissions in Aveiro36

Table 6: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Aveiro region38

Table 7: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of resident population unemployed and concentrations/emissions in Liguria41

Table 8: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Liguria region43

Table 9: Municipality boundary data and socio-economic data sources.....49

Table 10: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Bristol (n = 437)50

Table 11: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Amsterdam (n = 612)50

Table 12: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Aveiro region (n = 9111)51

Table 13: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Liguria region (n = 3284).....51

Executive Summary

There is increasing evidence that indicates that people from low socio-economic background are more likely to suffer from exposure to air pollution, which in turn creates health inequalities. Therefore, exploring and understanding distributive environmental justice in urban environments is important to understand the relationships between air pollution and socio-economic status. Bringing this evidence to citizens can help to raise environmental consciousness in underserved communities.

The spatial and temporal variations in emissions and concentrations coupled with individual and/or population demographics, practices and behaviours can result in disparities in exposure and related health risk and impacts. Thus, greater understanding of the relationships between air pollution and socio-economic status can achieve greater public health / air quality management integration. This integration can target action in high-need areas, coordinating air pollution mitigation and health improvement interventions and connecting different policy area.

Three analytical steps were applied in Bristol, Amsterdam, Aveiro and Liguria (no analysis was undertaken in Sosnowiec and Ljubljana as suitable sub-urban demographic data was not available). The analytic steps include:

1. Determining the area-weighted mean of air quality concentrations and total emissions to assess if any correlations exist between these and local indicators of socio-economic status.
2. Illustration of the spatial relationships between air pollution concentrations and local indicators of socio-economic status using bivariate maps.
3. Using population-weighted mean concentrations to explore variations in exposure for different demographic groups in each city/region.

For the ClairCity case study cities, the following can be concluded:

- Bristol: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD). Spatially the area of most concern is the city centre with some ethnic groups suffering more exposure than the population mean.
- Amsterdam: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the proportion of low-income households. Spatially and across different demographics, there are no notable variations, which may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the city population.
- Aveiro: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the proportion of low-income households. Spatially and across different demographics, there are no notable variations, which may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the city population and the low concentrations across the region.
- Liguria: There is there is a slight, but not statistical, tendency for unemployment to be positively correlated with concentrations data, but not emissions. Spatially the area of most concern is the Genoa Port area and to the east of the port. Some ethnic groups suffered more exposure than the population mean.
- For Sosnowiec and Ljubljana, no analysis could be undertaken at the sub-urban scale due to the lack of suitable demographic data.

Cities may have suitable data to derive meaningful conclusions but even in data rich cities, like Bristol and Amsterdam, the relationships and conclusions are often inconclusive. This may be due to a number of limitations related to the volume and quality of the spatial data; the analysis steps applied; and the stratification of the demographic data. Cities looking to undertake similar studies need to consider a number of process steps and overarching questions that go beyond understanding the distributional relationships and how that evidence can be used for targeted interventions. These include:

1. The suitability and availability of data at the right scales and the application of an appropriate analytical step.
2. Take care not to generalise the conclusions based on limited data and reflect on the suitability of the indicator of socio-economic status used.
3. The societal factors that help determine the exposure of different socio-economic groups.
4. How people can reduce their exposure and increase their resilience to air pollution.
5. The role that lifestyle factors and occupation may have in influencing the sensitivity and vulnerability and population groups.
6. The relative contribution of each pollutant and the cumulative impact of multiple air pollutants, multiple environmental stressors and wider determinants of public health.

1 Introduction

The scope of this study is to explore the linkages between indicators of socio-economic status and air pollution emissions and concentrations in the six case study cities and regions¹ in the ClairCity Project² (where suitable data exists). This includes a qualitative review of relevant literature related to the challenges of environmental justice and air pollution (Chapter 2) and a quantitative assessment of the air pollution emissions, concentration and demographic data in each case study city/region where suitable data is available (Chapter 3 and Chapter 4). The report concludes with recommendations for the case study cities and advice for other cities seeking to replicate our approach.

1.1 Approach and objectives

This report presents the findings of a literature review of environmental justice and air pollution coupled with a spatial analysis of the emissions, concentration and demographic data in each case study city/region. The geographical scope of the report captures a broad range of evidence from across Europe while also drawing upon international literature where relevant.

The key objectives are:

1. Review of relevant literature exploring the linkages between air pollution and indicators of socio-economic status.
2. Quantitative assessment of the spatial relationships between air pollution emissions and concentrations data with local demographic data across the ClairCity case study cities where data is available.
3. Recommendations for city partners and other cities seeking to replicate the quantitative methodological approach.

¹ The ClairCity case study cities and regions are: Bristol, United Kingdom; Amsterdam, Netherlands; Aveiro Region, Portugal; Sosnowiec, Poland; Ljubljana, Slovenia; and Liguria Region, Italy.

² An overview of the ClairCity process can be found in [Annex 2: Overview of the ClairCity Process](#)

2 Environmental Justice and Air Pollution

2.1 What is Environmental Justice?

Environmental justice has a number of definitions but the most commonly used is that by the US Environmental Protection Agency which defines it as:

“the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, colour, national origin, or income, with respect to the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies “

In simple terms, environmental justice explores the interlinked relationships of environmental issues (such as air pollution) and social determinants (such as deprivation) while considering the fairness of these relationships. Environmental justice has evolved from the wider social justice debate using the basic concept of ‘justice as fairness’ and two central principles of justice (Rawls, 1993). Government bodies are designed to be ‘just’ institutions and although the legislation that they generate is based on these principles of justice, their implementation can often disproportionately impact on vulnerable and marginalised communities. Laurent, (2011) recognised this legislation / implementation disconnection when reviewing a number of definitions used by organisations such as the OECD, UK Environment Agency and Scottish Government, concluding that environmental justice was a fourfold problem:

1. Exposure and Access Inequalities: unequal distribution of environmental quality between different individuals and groups;
2. Policy Effect Inequalities: the unequal effect of environmental policies;
3. Impact Inequalities: unequal environmental impact of different individuals and groups; and
4. Policy-making Inequalities: the unequal access to environmental policy making.

These four issues map onto the three concepts of environmental justice described by Walker (2012):

1. Distributive Justice: the distribution of environmental resources (positive impact) or environmental harms (negative impact);
2. Procedural Justice: how decisions are made and how individuals/communities are included (or excluded) from the decision-making process; and
3. Justice as recognition: the consideration of prejudice and discrimination.

The ClairCity project is interested in all three concepts of environmental justice. The central concept of the ClairCity project seeks to address the *procedural justice* issue by providing platforms to enable bottom-up citizen-led and citizen inclusive policymaking. However, this report is primarily concerned with the first concept, *distributive justice*, through understanding the relationships between air pollution emissions (the generation of pollution), air pollution concentrations/exposure (the potential harm from pollution) and indicators of socio-economic status and/or demographic data at the local scale. This *distributive justice* data can then be utilised to support *procedural justice* issues that citizens may face.

2.2 Air pollution, health and socio-economic status

Exposure to air pollution, such as particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), is linked to a number of health effects including respiratory and cardio-vascular disease. Air pollution has been recognised as a major cause of premature death and disease and is the single largest environmental health risk in Europe (WHO, 2014). Air pollution has a significant impact on the health of European citizens, particularly in urban areas, and was responsible for more than 400,000 premature deaths in Europe per year in the EEA-39 (excluding Turkey) (European Environmental Agency, 2019). The effects of air pollution vary not only due to exposure, but also due to the vulnerability of people including age, pre-existing health conditions and socio-economic status. Landrigan *et al.* (2018), identified that 92% of pollution related deaths globally occur in low-income and middle-income countries and, in countries at every income level, disease caused by pollution is most prevalent among minorities and marginalised communities.

These statistics provide a background to the scope and profile of the European air pollution exposure and health challenge, but they do not illustrate the local variation in air pollution emissions, concentrations, exposure and other burdens. It is within our cities that the public health impact is most acute as high air pollution concentrations and high population densities come together. This health impact is further exacerbated as air pollution exposure interacts with wider social determinants of health creating a disproportionate risk and burden (Brunt *et al.*, 2016). The local-level spatial and temporal variations in air pollution is influenced by factors such as road transport, residential solid-fuel combustion, industrial sources etc. These variations in emissions and concentrations coupled with individual and/or population practices and behaviours can result in disparities in exposure and related health risk and impacts. These individual and population level susceptibilities can be 'intrinsic' (e.g. age, sex genetics) and/or 'acquired' (e.g. income, education, housing, employment, service access, and lifestyle/behaviour related chronic illnesses) (Brunt *et al.*, 2016; Fann *et al.*, 2015; Lipfert, 2004).

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (2008/50/EC) and EU Member State frameworks, 'simplify' the process of air quality management by seeking to keep ambient concentrations of pollutants below specified health-based thresholds. However, it is now over two decades since the 1996 European Framework Directive on Ambient Air Quality was introduced, sixteen years since the PM₁₀ limit values came into force (2004) and ten years since the nitrogen dioxide limit values came into force (2010), and still a substantial number of European Member States exceed the limit values for NO₂ and PM₁₀, from sources such as road transport and domestic solid fuel burning. Given the widespread non-compliance with the Ambient Air Quality Directive and continue substantial health impacts across Europe, it is time to consider why this policy process has failed and how more effective approaches to air quality management might be implemented. Closing the disconnection between air quality management and public health policy and practice can ensure more targeted and co-ordinated action resulting in reductions in air pollution and population-level risks and inequalities.

2.3 Qualitative assessment of the links between air pollution and socio-economic status

In 2018, the European Environment Agency commissioned a qualitative and quantitative assessment of the relationships between air pollution, noise and socio-economic status (European Environment Agency, 2018). Additionally, Fairburn *et al.*, (2019), undertook a systematic review of literature related to social inequalities in exposure to ambient air pollution in the WHO European region. These reports provide a comprehensive review of the current literature and evidence and concludes that the burden of higher pollutants falls disproportionately on different social groups. This report does not seek to replicate these comprehensive systematic literature assessments, but does draw upon the key findings to support the need for assessment at the city scale.

2.3.1 European Policy

Multiple international strategies such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement regularly recognise and explicitly state the need and importance for policies and interventions to ensure that the most vulnerable communities are protected against environmental impacts. While these, and EU level strategies, identify this need, they do not include actions that actually address inequalities rather than just ensuring a good-quality environment for all.

The EEA qualitative assessment (Barnes *et al.*, 2018) undertook a review of EU environmental policy to consider both generic mentions of social inequality or socio-economic status and/or references to specific drivers of inequality. The study found that, overall, the inclusion of socio-economic factors with both overarching environmental objectives and more sector-specific environmental directives is mixed – strategic, longer-term documents generally refer to societal challenges and link environmental protection to social inequality, but sector-specific directives have a weaker consideration.

At a global level, initiatives such as the Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations, and the EU's approach to pursuing the SDGs, A Global Partnership for Poverty Eradication and Sustainable Development after 2015 and Next Steps for a Sustainable European Future, place social equity centrally in their consideration of environmental protection.

At an EU level, linkages between air pollution and socio-economic status are evident in a number of strategies such as Health 2020 Strategy and the Declaration of the Sixth Ministerial Conference of Environment and Health. Some strategies recognise the need to design interventions to support groups at particular risk and sets ambitious poverty, climate change, and resource efficiency targets (e.g. Europe 2020 Strategy) while others refer to the need to integrate environmental, social and economic accounting systems (e.g. 2011 Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe) but the linkages and interplay between these issues are not assessed.

Specific to air pollution, the 2005 Thematic Strategy on Air Pollution addresses the impact of air pollution on citizen's health and identifies that some groups are more vulnerable than others, but these are not defined based on socio-economic factors. This is also evident in the

Ambient Air Quality Directive (2008/50/EC) that includes references of sensitive populations and the need to estimate the number of people exposed to poor air quality but it does not require the consideration of socio-economic factors when implementing the Directive or when developing air quality plans. The National Emissions Ceiling Directive (2016/2284/EU) and the Medium Combustion Plants Directive (2015/2193) does not mention the consideration of citizens from disadvantaged backgrounds or their consideration when developing emission control policies.

In a European legislative context, the concepts of procedural justice and justice as recognition, are seen to be addressed, although there appears to be a disconnection between the legislative intention and its interpretation / implementation. For example, the Ambient Air Quality Directive (2008/50/EC) clearly states the importance of providing information to the public (Article 26 and Annex XVI) but much of this information at an EU, national or local level is predominantly provided electronically via the internet and assumes that all of the public has the resources to access this information. Barnes et al. (2018) concluded that “*the analysis suggests that while higher level and longer term strategic documents within an environmental scope are likely to include references to socio-economic factors, with some of them also looking at the interplay between social deprivation and exposure, the environmental directives do not integrate these aspects to date*”.

2.3.2 Understanding relationships at differing spatial scales of impact

A 2013 pan-European study stated that PM₁₀ levels were approximately 30% higher and the long term O₃ concentrations were 30-40% higher in the most disadvantaged regions compared to the wealthiest regions (Richardson *et al.*, 2013). The quantitative assessment supporting the European Environment Agency, (2018) study primarily focussed on the annual means of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} and the SOMO35³ indicator for O₃. This pollution data is based on the interpolated 1km by 1km concentration grids. This data is combined with population data to calculate population weighted average concentrations for each NUTS region or city⁴. The association between exposure to air pollution and levels of social vulnerability varied substantially across Europe depending on the pollutant, the vulnerability factor and the spatial unit of assessment considered. Generally, areas characterised by lower socio-economic status tended to have higher levels of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and O₃ but the converse was true for NO₂ where areas with higher economic status generally experience higher levels of NO₂ pollution (Figure 1)⁵.

- For PM (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}), regions characterised by lower socio-economic status tended to have higher exposure. Most of the NUTS-2 regions in both the top 20% of PM₁₀ exposure and the top 20% of long-term unemployment rate were found in Bulgaria, Greece and parts of Italy, Spain and Slovakia. Extensive areas of south-eastern Europe and Italy are in the top 20% of high exposure to PM_{2.5} and the most deprived 20% regarding higher education qualifications.

³ The sum of means over 35 parts per billion (daily maximum 8-hour) is the yearly sum of the daily maximum of 8-hour running average over 35 ppb.

⁴ Full details of the methodological approach can be found in German *et al.*, (2018)

⁵ Source European Environment Agency, 2018

- For O₃, regions with a higher proportion of people without tertiary education also tended to have higher exposure to O₃. The NUTS-2 regions in the bottom 20% for higher education qualifications and the top 20% for O₃ exposure are all found in southern Europe in Greece, Italy and Portugal. This may be as a consequence of the geographic variation of O₃ with higher concentrations in southern Europe.
- For NO₂, regions with higher socio-economic indicators also had higher exposure to NO₂ concentrations. At NUTS-2 level, average concentrations for regions in the top 20% of household income was 1.5 times higher than in the regions with the lowest income. This reflects the higher volumes of urbanisation and the higher volumes of traffic in densely populated regions including northern Italy, Germany and the United Kingdom.

Note: The shading represents the values of the Spearman's correlation coefficient, which measures association between aspects of social vulnerability and exposure to extreme temperatures (see Box 3.2). Positive values (in red) indicate that higher vulnerability tends to correspond to higher exposure levels; negative values (in blue) indicate that higher vulnerability tends to correspond to lower exposure levels. The intensity of the colour explains the strengths of the association.

(*) With the exception of associations between social vulnerability indicators and NO₂, where average concentrations were taken during the period 2011-2012.

Source: Based on ETC/ACM (2018a).

6

Figure 1: Associations between exposure to air pollutants and indicators of social vulnerability across Europe

At the national or city scales, studies generally show a positive correlation between deprivation and worse environmental conditions but the relationships can be further complicated depending on the socio-spatial distribution of sources, relevant exposure and the impact of multiple stressors. National and city level studies have found that people of lower economic status often live in areas with higher volumes of traffic leading to higher levels of air pollution e.g. in the UK (Barnes, Chatterton and Longhurst, 2019; Paavola, 2017), Germany (Flacke *et al.*, 2016; Franck, Klimeczek and Kindler, 2014) and France (Padilla *et al.*, 2016). Within cities, specific patterns of spatial inequalities and infant /neonatal mortality over time can be observed (Padilla *et al.*, 2016). Across major urban areas such as London, populations living in the most deprived areas are on average more exposed to poor air quality than those in less deprived areas: 46% of the LSOAs within the most deprived 10% of London have concentrations above the NO₂ EU limit value, compared with 2% above the NO₂ EU limit values in the 10% least deprived areas (Brook and King, 2017). While at a national level, an assessment of the relationship between air pollution, health and socio-economic status in Wales found that all-

⁶ Source European Environment Agency, 2018

cause and respiratory disease mortality rates were highest in the most deprived areas and air pollution strengthened the effect of deprivation on health (Brunt *et al.*, 2017).

2.3.3 Consider the relationship when developing interventions

The assessment of environmental justice from the perspective of distributional justice is not only relevant when considering spatial and temporal relationships but it is also essential when considering the development and implementation of interventions. Numerous studies considering air pollution and carbon emissions / climate change have shown the negative impact that poorly planned interventions can have on social equity. Conversely, studies have also shown the positive impact that policy / interventions that consider social equity and proactively engage all stakeholder communities can have. For example, accessibility to green infrastructure (Silva and Panagopoulos, 2018); interventions aimed at improving the quality of housing (Poortinga, Dunstan and Fone, 2008); active travel (Olsen *et al.*, 2017), environmental taxes on goods (García-Muros *et al.*, 2017); reducing in domestic solid fuel burning (Bailey *et al.*, 2019) and even the perception of air quality (Deguen, Padilla and Padilla, 2017).

Shrestha *et al.*, (2016) explored multiple burdens and benefits, in combination with vulnerability factors at detailed intra-urban areas, in Dortmund, Germany. They concluded that understanding these relationships is essential to mobilise local stakeholders and can serve as a basis to develop interventions that target vulnerable groups to ensure a health-conducive equal environment. From a transport perspective, there are three core dimensions where inequalities are apparent: exposure, distribution of space and valuation of transport time. The public and political recognition of these urban transport inequalities is important to drive significant changes in urban planning, transport infrastructure development and traffic management (Gössling, 2016). National small scale analyses in the UK in 2001 showed that poor air quality was more prevalent in socio-economically deprived areas, and over the subsequent decade air quality improvements were greatest in the least deprived areas, whilst the most deprived areas bore a disproportionate and rising share of declining air quality including non-compliance with air quality standards (Mitchell, Norman and Mullin, 2015).

The evidence suggests that consideration of environmental justice in decision making is an important step to reduce inequalities but this is often an analysis step missing from city-scale assessments. In the UK, to work towards compliance with EU Limit Values, many local authorities were tasked with assessing the feasibility of Clean Air Zones within their administrative areas (i.e. the restriction of specific vehicles in certain areas). Part of these feasibility studies included an assessment of the social equity of Clean Air Zones as an intervention and many authorities cited equity as one of the primary reasons for not pursuing a Class D Clean Air Zone which would have included private vehicles. In California, US, a study that considered the implementation of low emission zones and HGV-rerouting, highlighted potential trade-offs and win-win outcomes (Nguyen and Marshall, 2018). The study suggested that a simple, straightforward approach – reducing emissions in neighbourhoods with a high proportion of minority residents – may or may not yield the maximum benefits, but to truly understand the impact of interventions you need to consider four outcomes: (1) total pollution exposure; (2) exposure efficiency (exposure impact per unit of emissions); (3) exposure inequality (deviations from exposure being equally distributed across the population; unequal exposure among individuals); and exposure injustice (associations between exposure and demographic attributes; unequal exposure among groups). Brunt *et al.*, (2018) argued for

greater public health integration and engagement with air quality management policy and practice to improve risk assessment and raise awareness of air pollution and other health influencing relationships. This greater integration can target action in high-need areas, coordinating air pollution mitigation and health improvement interventions and connecting different policy area. The first step to achieve this is to understand the local relationships between air pollution and indicators of socio-economic status.

3 Methodology and Data Sources

The following chapter outlines the data sources and methodological steps implemented to undertake the distributive justice assessment. Air pollution emissions and concentration data is available at a suitable spatial scale from the ClairCity project for all case studies. However, accessing secondary data relating to socio-economic status and geographical data for municipalities across each of the ClairCity cities and regions at an appropriate spatial scale for analysis against the concentrations and emissions gridded data has been challenging.

The European Environment Agency, (2018) study worked with a 1km by 1km grid but concluded that due to the scale of the analysis, the value does not reflect the probably large variations in concentrations within the grids (i.e. at a lower scale). Interventions tackling environmental health inequalities need to be based on an assessment of their magnitude and the identification of population groups that are most exposed or most vulnerable to environmental risk. However, data to quantify the baseline situation is not abundant therefore making comprehensive assessments difficult at national and local levels. The ClairCity air quality modelling approach has emissions and concentration data at 200m by 200m resolution but this also has its issues as the socio-economic and demographic data, if available, is normally at a higher scale. Within this study, suitable scale socio-economic and demographic data is only available for Bristol, Amsterdam, Aveiro and Liguria. Unfortunately, this data is not available for Ljubljana and Sosnowiec, therefore, analysis at this fine scale could not be completed for these cities.

A full breakdown of the data sources assessed and utilised can be found in [Annex 1: Data Sources](#).

3.1 Spatial air pollution emission and concentration data

The following is a brief synopsis of the air quality emissions and concentrations methodology implemented by the ClairCity project. A full detailed modelling methodology and datasets can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/claircity>

3.1.1 Overarching approach

The baseline characterisation for all case studies was performed using an integrated modelling toolset that included the following modules:

1. Integrated urban module
2. Emissions modules
 - a. Transport module
 - b. Industrial, residential, commerce and institutional module (IRCI)
 - c. Energy / Power Generation module
 - d. Nature / Agriculture module
3. Air quality dispersion model
4. Population exposure module
5. Health effects and cost module

6. Carbon footprint module

The assessment framework operates as a chain process and was developed considering local GIS and case study specific available datasets (e.g. emissions inventories, air quality monitoring data, road networks, land-use data etc.) calibrated against baseline / current monitoring data.

3.1.2 Air Quality Emissions Data

The geographical scope of the emissions was considered at three distinct levels:

1. The emissions within the city / region boundaries
2. The emissions outside the city / region boundaries, but close enough to influence air quality within the city / region; and
3. The emissions outside the city / region boundaries, which have no impact on air quality within the city / region but are relevant for carbon footprint assessment.

Each module played a specific step in generating the spatial emissions data used in this assessment:

- The Integrated Urban Module focussed on activity-behaviour data while considering land-use and household choices with a direct or indirect effect on emissions, such as:
 - Geographical and temporal demands for transport.
 - Housing and residential energy consumption
 - Consumption of good
- The Transport module is primarily driven by the technological composition of the car fleet and the speed and adoption of electric vehicles. The module used COPERT emissions factors and worked across three layers:
 - City fleet model
 - Mode choice
 - Network assignment
- The IRCI module integrated distinct emissions sources and was built using existing industrial emissions data (EMEP and E-PRTR) and EMEP/EEA Emissions Inventory Guidebook. Additionally, combustion from small residential, commercial and institutional sectors were included.
- The Energy/Power module explores annual/hourly energy consumption at the household level spatially and temporally across the case studies.

These modules have generated GIS emissions layers for NO_x, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} at 200m by 200m resolution for this analysis.

3.1.3 Air Quality Concentration Data

The air quality concentration data was calculated at a number of scales and then verified and if necessary adjusted against local monitoring data.

1. At the mesoscale, the modelling was performed using the WRF-CAMx modelling system. The European domain covering all of the case studies was simulated with 0.25

degrees horizontal grid resolution. The regional domain covering the six case studies was simulated with 0.05 degrees of horizontal resolution.

2. The Particulate Matter Source Apportionment Tool (PSAT) was used to assess the contribution from different emissions sectors.
3. The URBAIR model was run at the urban scale for each case study with a horizontal resolution of 200m by 200m.

This model generated GIS air quality concentration layers for NO₂ and PM₁₀ at 200m by 200m resolution for this analysis.

3.2 Spatial socio-economic status data

Spatial socio-economic status data at a suitable scale is difficult to obtain across the six case studies cities especially at a scale suitable to undertake interrelationship analysis with the emission and concentration data. Subsequently, this analysis has used actual and surrogate where available but not all case studies had this so extrapolations from national and pan-European analysis were considered.

For Bristol, it was possible to use the English Indices of Deprivation 2019 at the Lower Super Output Area (LSOA) scale (equivalent to LAU2). In the remaining cities and regions, however, it was necessary to use proxies for socio-economic status, such as income, employment or activity level. In Amsterdam, employment and social assistance benefits data⁷ were available at the neighbourhood (Buurt) level, but inconsistently across the study area; i.e. only in the central areas. Household level income data was also provided by ClairCity project partner, PBL, but aggregated into 'low/medium/high' income levels.

In Aveiro, employment/ unemployment/ retiree census data could be linked to municipal level geography. Finer scale (parish) geographic data was provided by PBL, but no related deprivation data or suitable proxy could be identified at that scale. In Liguria, data relating to taxpayers⁸ was available at the municipality (community) scale⁹, however, this geographic scale was too coarse for comparison against the concentrations and emissions gridded data. Finer resolution census sections (sez cens) data was provided by PBL, but no relatable deprivation data were available. Studies have identified the construction of a Genoa Deprivation Index¹⁰, however, it has not been possible to obtain this in a usable form, prompting the use of unemployment data as a proxy measure. Activity rate, employment and unemployment data has been obtained for Ljubljana at the municipality level, however, at present it has not been possible to link to equivalent settlement level geographies. For Sosnowiec, neighbourhood level geographies were provided by PBL, but no equivalent scale deprivation data or proxies have been identified.

⁷ <https://data.amsterdam.nl/datasets/XexhCp7LgdryfA/werk-en-inkomen-buurten/>

⁸ http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=MEF_REDDITIIRPEF_COM

⁹ <https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/222527>

¹⁰ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11205-017-1720-3#Sec17>

3.3 Area-weighted spatial analysis

Spatial analysis of the concentrations and emissions gridded data and socioeconomic status was conducted using ArcGIS Pro (v 2.4). Shapefiles of the geographic datasets (e.g. LSOA in Bristol) and tables of the concentrations, emissions and socioeconomic status were added to the GIS and joined using appropriate geographic identifiers. NO₂/PM₁₀/PM_{2.5} concentrations were proportionally averaged across each municipality area, weighted by area, against the LSOA fraction intersecting with each grid cell. For example, if quarter of a LSOA fell within a grid cell with 40 µg/m³ and the other three-quarters fell within another with 60 µg/m³ the concentration attributed to the LSOA would be (25% × 40 µg/m³)+(75% × 60 µg/m³) = 55 µg/m³. Conversely, NO_x/PM emissions were area-weighted based on the fraction of grid cells covered by each municipality area. For example, if a LSOA fell across half of a grid cell with 10 t/km² and the whole of another with 15 t/km² the emission attributed to the LSOA would be (50% × 10 t/km²)+(100% × 15 t/km²) = 20 t/km². Without finer resolution data, with which to reveal the degree of variability within these areas, this approach assumes uniformity of average concentrations across each LSOA and emissions over each individual grid cell.

Figure 2: Spatial analysis process

Additionally, bivariate maps have been generated for each case study city for the following:

- Total NO₂ concentration and local socio-economic status indicator
- Total PM₁₀ concentration and local socio-economic status indicator
- Total PM_{2.5} concentration and local socio-economic status indicator

The bivariate map displays two variables on a single map by combining two different sets of graphic symbols or colours. It is important to note that the bivariate maps is not an illustration of 'good' or 'bad' areas of air pollution but it is a variation of a simple choropleth map that portrays two separate datasets simultaneously and therefore allows the reader to visualise the spatial relationships across the study areas. The classifications varied for each city/region depending on the minimum and maximum concentrations and socio-economic status indicator. Depending on the distribution of the data, this resulted in a 3 x 3 bivariate map but others were only 2 x 2.

3.4 Population-weighted analysis

When exploring environmental justice and/or air pollution exposure inequalities at a high spatial scale (e.g. across a city region, nationally, or EU), the population-weighted mean concentration methodology is commonly applied (German *et al.*, 2018; COMEAP, 2010). The methodology, while quite simplistic, allows the estimation of pollution 'exposure' on specific demographics across a specific geography assuming that the concentration-response function is linear and with no threshold. Using this summary statistic allows the consideration of the vulnerability of specific subsets of demographics (e.g. gender, age, and ethnicity). The indicators used varied from case study to case study depending on availability.

The population weighted mean is calculated by multiplying the area-weighted annual mean concentration (calculated in Section 3.3) for each spatial area (e.g. LSOA in Bristol) and the population of that spatial area (e.g. total population or a demographic sub-set such as the number of males/females). The values for all of the spatial areas were summed and the divided by the total population of the study area (or total demographic subset) to calculate the population-weighted mean. These demographic sub-set weighted means can be used to compare against the total population-weighted mean to determine if a specific demographic is more or less 'exposed'.

3.5 Study Limitations

One common theme across the other city scale studies is the limitations depending on the availability of relevant data at a suitable scale to undertake the assessment. For this study there are a number of limitations that need to be considered when reviewing the outcomes:

1. The ability to undertake the analysis is entirely dependent on the availability of data and indicators at a suitable local scale. Subsequently, no analysis has been undertaken at this time for Sosnowiec and Ljubljana due to a lack of demographic/socio-economic data at sub city scale.

2. The stratification of data to the local scale or to smaller demographics can 'hide' sub-urban characteristics resulting in increased uncertainty. Therefore, when considering environmental justice, it is important to reflect carefully on the analysis used as one methodology alone or a single socio-demographic indicator may not show any issues but the application of different tests may show a different picture.
3. Population-weighted means is a commonly used approach for large national and regional studies. It has been used at the city scale but care should be taken with the interpretation of the evidence and not to over-generalise the conclusions as it is heavily influenced by the suitability and stratification of the demographic data and the local variance of the area-weighted mean.
4. Datasets are not necessarily taken from the same year e.g. decennial census data, however the lack of annual variability means that this is unlikely to have an influence on the correlations.
5. A lack of meaningful trends in the socio-economic status and emissions / concentration correlation analysis does not mean that social inequalities do not exist in a specific region. The small scale of the study area and the limited data can restrict this analysis and 'hide' areas that exist but are not statistically significant.

4 Relationships between air quality emissions, concentrations and socio-economic status.

The following section provides a synopsis of the key results generated by the area-weighted and population weighted analysis of the air pollution emissions, concentrations and socio-economic / demographic data across the case studies where data is available. The results are presented on a case study by case study basis with city specific discussion. Additionally, bivariate maps are provided to illustrate locations of specific interest (please note the classifications of the bivariate maps, these are not maps of 'good' or 'bad' but instead an indicator of inequities).

4.1 Bristol, United Kingdom

4.1.1 Area-weighted spatial analysis (Bristol)

For Bristol, the concentrations and emissions gridded data were spatially attributed to Lower Super Output Areas (LSOAs) obtained from the UK Office for National Statistics using the methodology defined in Section 3.3. LSOAs have a relatively consistent population size (~700 households (range 400–1200), ~1600 residents (range 1000–3000) nationally) and, importantly, a greater degree of uniformity in terms of socioeconomic characteristics, thereby limiting the ecological fallacy inherent in area census data analysis (Openshaw, 1984), i.e. the risk of misrepresenting the socioeconomic characteristics of individuals, based on analyses undertaken on the LSOAs in which they reside, is reduced. English Indices of Deprivation 2019 were obtained from the UK Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government and were joined to the Bristol LSOAs by ID field. Plots were then created in ArcGIS Pro for the spatially attributed concentrations (NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) and emissions (NO_x, PM) respectively against the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) rank scores for each LSOA.

Plots for Total NO₂ concentrations, PM₁₀ concentrations, PM_{2.5} concentrations, NO_x emissions and PM emissions are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Whilst there is clearly a lot of noise in the data, and no significant trend in the correlation between concentrations or emissions and IMD, there is a slight trend towards areas with the lowest rank of IMD (i.e. the most deprived LSOAs) having higher concentrations of NO₂ than areas with the highest rank of IMD. This is in line with national trends (see Section 3), which more clearly indicate a strong positive correlation with deprivation and exposure to NO₂ concentrations. Spearman's rank analysis (Table 1) also reveals that there is no clear statistical correlation.

The lack of clarity in this relationship at the city scale in Bristol may be due to variability in the data, with some of the least deprived areas located within the city centre where NO₂ concentrations tend to be higher, and areas of high deprivation located on the periphery of Bristol, i.e. away from the highest NO₂ concentrations.

Figure 3: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol

Figure 4: Scatter plot of NOx (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol

Table 1: Spearman's rank correlation of Index Multiple Deprivation and concentrations/emissions in Bristol

Spearman's Rank Correlation in Bristol					
	NO ₂ concentrations	PM ₁₀ concentrations	PM _{2.5} concentrations	NOx emissions	PM emissions
Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) Rank	-0.1864	-0.0765	-0.1156	-0.2477	-0.0995

4.1.2 Bivariate maps (Bristol)

Figure 5: Bivariate map of NO₂ (left), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations against Index of Multiple Deprivation Rank for Bristol

The bivariate maps of Bristol (Figure 5) illustrates the relationships between NO₂ concentration and Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD), PM₁₀ concentrations and IMD and PM_{2.5} concentrations and IMD. While there is some spatial variation across the city, the highest concentrations and highest IMD are located in the city centre locations (red). The relationship for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations with IMD is larger than for NO₂ but the concentrations are quite low. However, as PM can be considered a non-threshold pollutant, understanding these spatial relationships are important especially when considering the cumulative burden of multiple pollutants.

4.1.3 Population-weighted analysis (Bristol)

The population-weighted mean concentration for NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Bristol is 24.8, 12.9 and 9.3 µg/m³ respectively (Table 4). The following notable differences are observed across each pollutant and demographic characteristics:

- NO₂ population weighted means:
 - There is a 2.3 µg/m³ increase and a similar decrease in exposure for µg/m³ for people aged 16-24 and 65+ respectively.
 - There is a notable 3.7 µg/m³, 5.1 µg/m³, 7.9 µg/m³ and 5.6 µg/m³ increase in exposure for Mixed, Asian, Black and Other Ethnic groups respectively.
- PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} population weighted means:
 - There is no notable increased or decreased exposure across different age or ethnic groupings although a slight increased concentration, similar to NO₂ but of smaller magnitude is noted again for certain ethnic groups.

The description statistics for these demographic categories can be found in [Annex 1: Data Sources](#).

Table 2: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Bristol

Description	NO ₂ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM ₁₀ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM _{2.5} Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)	
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference
Total Population	24.84	-	12.96	-	9.28	-
Age 0-15	24.39	-0.45	12.89	-0.07	9.19	-0.09
Age 16-24	27.11	2.26	13.28	0.32	9.59	0.31
Age 25-44	26.25	1.14	13.27	0.31	9.58	0.31
Age 45-64	23.51	-1.34	12.73	-0.23	9.05	-0.22
Age >65	22.58	-2.26	12.49	-0.47	8.82	-0.45
White	24.09	-0.76	12.84	-0.12	9.16	-0.11
Mixed / Multiple Ethnic Groups	28.52	3.67	13.68	0.72	9.98	0.70
Asian / Asian British	29.90	5.06	13.72	0.76	9.95	0.68
Black / African / Caribbean / Black British	32.69	7.85	14.27	1.31	10.43	1.16
Other	30.49	5.65	13.87	0.91	10.09	0.81

4.2 Amsterdam, The Netherlands

4.2.1 Area-weighted spatial analysis (Amsterdam)

In Amsterdam, neighbourhood-scale geographic data was in the form of 'Buurten'. Central Amsterdam Buurten were obtained from Gemeente Amsterdam, whilst the peripheral areas were obtained from The Netherlands Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS). These were merged together to form one dataset covering all Amsterdam Buurten with concentrations and emissions modelled data being attributed to the Buurten, as per Section 3.3.

Household income data was obtained from PBL as a proxy for deprivation statistics in Amsterdam. These were provided as point data files with categorical income bands: high, medium and low. To enable analysis of 'deprivation' against the Buurten level geography, the point data were spatially joined to the merged geographic data file in GIS, summarised on the Buurten geography to calculate the number of households within that Buurt in each income band. From this, the proportion of households in the low-income band in each Buurt was calculated and plotted against the concentrations and emissions data for each Buurt.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the plots of the proportion of households in the low-income band against NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations and NO_x and PM emissions. As with Bristol, and indicated by the Spearman's rank analysis (Table 3), there is no apparent correlation between the variables, suggesting that the income levels of households across the Buurt-scale geographies may be heterogeneous.

Table 3: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of households in low-income band and concentrations/emissions in Amsterdam

Spearman's Rank Correlation for Amsterdam					
	NO ₂ concentrations	PM ₁₀ concentrations	PM _{2.5} concentrations	NO _x emissions	PM emissions
Proportion of households in low income band	-0.1044	-0.0971	-0.1249	0.0040	-0.0337

Figure 6: Scatter plot of NO_2 (top), PM_{10} (centre) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (bottom) concentrations against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam

Figure 7: Scatter plot of NOx (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam

4.2.2 Bivariate maps (Amsterdam)

Figure 8: Bivariate map of NO₂ (left), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations against the proportion of households in the low-income band for Amsterdam

The bivariate maps of Amsterdam are only 2 x 2 due to the distribution of the air pollution concentrations. Figure 8 illustrates the relationships between NO₂ concentration and proportion of low-income households, PM₁₀ concentrations and proportion of low-income households and PM_{2.5} concentrations and proportion of low-income households. While there is some spatial variation across the city, the highest concentrations and proportion of households with low income are located outside of the city centre (dark yellow). There are locations in the city centre with a high classification of air pollution but also have high income (dark green). The concentrations for all pollutants are quite low across the city for all pollutants. The lack of condensed locations with high pollution and low income, may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the Amsterdam population and the low concentrations experience across the city.

4.2.3 Population-weighted analysis (Amsterdam)

The population-weighted mean concentration for NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Amsterdam is 27.3, 16.8 and 11.3 µg/m³ respectively (Table 4). There are no notable differences across the demographic categories or pollutants, which again may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the Amsterdam population.

The description statistics for these demographic categories can be found in [Annex 1: Data Sources](#).

Table 4: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Amsterdam

Description	NO ₂ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM ₁₀ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM _{2.5} Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)	
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference
Total Population	27.32	-	16.83	-	11.26	-
Male	27.47	0.15	16.85	0.03	11.29	0.03
Female	27.14	-0.18	16.80	-0.03	11.23	-0.03
High Income	27.94	0.63	16.96	0.13	11.40	0.14
Medium Income	27.45	0.14	16.84	0.01	11.27	0.01
Low Income	27.07	-0.25	16.76	-0.04	11.22	-0.04
Age 15-44	27.11	-0.21	16.79	-0.03	11.22	-0.04
Age 45-64	27.61	0.30	16.88	0.05	11.33	0.07
Age >65	27.37	0.06	16.83	0.00	11.26	-0.01
Dutch	27.51	0.19	16.89	0.06	11.31	0.05
Foreign	27.06	-0.26	16.74	-0.08	11.19	-0.07

4.3 Aveiro Region, Portugal

4.3.1 Area-weighted spatial analysis (Aveiro)

Neighbourhood-level geographic data, linked to census variables for buildings, households and individuals, were obtained from the University of Aveiro, for the whole of Baixo Vouga, the Portuguese sub-region centred around the city of Aveiro. The modelled concentrations and emissions datasets were attributed to the neighbourhood-scale geographies following the methodology in section 3.3. Of the census variables available at this scale, indicator N_IND_R_16, Resident individuals without economic activity, was used as a proxy for unemployment, as it was considered the most representative indicator of deprivation.

Plots of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations and NO_x and PM emissions against the number of resident individuals without economic activity are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. There is no clear trend indicated by any of the plots, and, although there is a slight positive correlation in concentrations against unemployment, there is too much noise in the data to suggest any relationship at this scale. Spearman's rank confirms the lack of statistical correlation (Table 5).

Figure 9: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro

Figure 10: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro

Table 5: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of resident individuals without economic activity and concentrations/emissions in Aveiro

Spearman's Rank Correlation for Aveiro					
	NO ₂ concentrations	PM ₁₀ concentrations	PM _{2.5} concentrations	NO _x emissions	PM emissions
Resident individuals without economic activity	0.1830	0.2222	0.2268	0.0489	0.0604

4.3.2 Bivariate Maps (Aveiro)

The bivariate maps of Aveiro (Figure 11) illustrate the relationships between NO₂ concentration and unemployment; PM₁₀ concentrations and employment; and PM_{2.5} concentrations and unemployment. While there is some spatial variation across the region, the highest concentrations and highest unemployment for NO₂ are located in the Aveiro city locations (red). The relationship for PM₁₀ concentrations with unemployment is substantially larger to the north, south-south-west and including the Aveiro urban area but all concentrations are very low. PM_{2.5} had only isolated small areas with Class 3 PM_{2.5} concentrations and Class 3 unemployment. Although concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are low, as PM can be considered a non-threshold pollutant, understanding these spatial relationships are important especially when considering the cumulative burden of multiple pollutants.

Figure 11: Bivariate map of NO_2 (left), PM_{10} (centre) and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (right) concentrations against resident individuals without economic activity for Aveiro

4.3.3 Population-weighted analysis (Aveiro)

The population-weighted mean concentration for NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Aveiro is 13.2, 12.1 and 10.0 µg/m³ respectively (Table 6). There are no notable differences across the demographic categories or pollutants, which may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the Aveiro population and the low concentrations across the region.

The description statistics for these demographic categories can be found in [Annex 1: Data Sources](#).

Table 6: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Aveiro region

Description	NO ₂ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM ₁₀ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM _{2.5} Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)	
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference
Total Population	13.19	-	12.07	-	10.02	-
Male	13.15	-0.04	12.06	-0.01	10.02	0.00
Female	13.23	0.03	12.07	0.00	10.02	0.00
Age 0-14	13.20	0.01	12.08	0.01	10.03	0.01
Age 15-24	13.13	-0.06	12.07	0.00	10.02	0.00
Age 24-64	13.29	0.10	12.08	0.01	10.02	0.00
Age >64	12.91	-0.28	12.02	-0.05	10.01	-0.01
Employed	13.37	0.18	12.08	0.01	10.03	0.01
Unemployed	12.96	-0.23	12.04	-0.03	10.01	-0.02

4.4 Liguria Region, Italy

4.4.1 Area-weighted spatial analysis (Liguria)

In Liguria, the Genova Sezioni di censimento (census sections) for the D3 region were used as the local neighbourhood-scale geographies. These were provided by PBL. 2011 population and housing census variables for the region were obtained from the Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (Istat). Variable P62: Resident population (15 years and above) unemployed seeking new employment, was selected as the most representative indicator of deprivation, and plotted against the concentrations and emissions modelled data as per Section 3.3.

The plots of unemployment against NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations and NO_x and PM emissions are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Although there is a lot of noise in the data, there is a slight tendency for unemployment to be positively correlated with concentrations data, but not emissions. Spearman's rank analysis, however, reveals that the correlation between unemployment and concentrations is very weak (Table 7).

Figure 12: Scatter plot of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident population unemployed for Liguria

Figure 13: Scatter plot of NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions against resident population unemployed for Liguria

Table 7: Spearman's rank correlation of the proportion of resident population unemployed and concentrations/emissions in Liguria

Spearman's Rank Correlation in Liguria					
	NO ₂ concentrations	PM ₁₀ concentrations	PM _{2.5} concentrations	NO _x emissions	PM emissions
Resident population (15 years and above) unemployed seeking new employment	0.1830	0.2222	0.2268	0.0489	0.0604

4.4.2 Bivariate Maps (Liguria)

The bivariate maps of Liguria (Figure 14) illustrate the relationships between NO₂ concentration and unemployment; PM₁₀ concentrations and unemployment; and PM_{2.5} concentrations and unemployment. While there is some spatial variation across the region, the highest concentrations and highest unemployment for NO₂ are around the Genoa port region (red). The relationship for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations with unemployment is more dispersed but again there are pockets of interest in the vicinity of Genoa port, and to the east of the port area. Although concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are relatively low, as PM can be considered a non-threshold pollutant, understanding these spatial relationships are important especially when considering the cumulative burden of multiple pollutants.

Figure 14: Bivariate map of NO₂ (top), PM₁₀ (centre) and PM_{2.5} (bottom) concentrations against resident population unemployed for Liguria

4.4.3 Population-weighted analysis (Liguria)

The population-weighted mean concentration for NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in Liguria is 23.7, 22.9 and 17.6 µg/m³ respectively (Table 8). The following notable differences are observed across each pollutant and demographic characteristics:

- NO₂ population weighted means:
 - There is a notable 3.7 µg/m³, 4.7 µg/m³ and 6.2 µg/m³ increase in exposure for African, American and Asian Ethnic groups respectively.
- PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} population weighted means:
 - There is no notable increased or decreased exposure across different age or ethnic groupings although a slight increased concentration, similar to NO₂ but of smaller magnitude is noted again for Asian ethnic group.

The description statistics for these demographic categories can be found in [Annex 1: Data Sources](#).

Table 8: Population Weighted Mean Concentrations for each demographic in Liguria region

Description	NO ₂ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM ₁₀ Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)		PM _{2.5} Pop-Weight Conc (µg/m ³)	
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference
Total Population	23.73	-	22.88	-	17.55	-
Male	23.69	-0.04	22.84	-0.04	17.53	-0.02
Female	23.76	0.04	22.92	0.04	17.57	0.02
0-14	23.64	-0.09	22.80	-0.08	17.51	-0.04
15-24	23.95	0.22	22.87	-0.01	17.55	-0.01
25-44	23.83	0.20	22.85	-0.03	17.54	-0.02
44-64	23.65	-0.07	22.85	-0.03	17.54	-0.20
>64	23.69	-0.04	22.97	0.09	17.60	0.05
Employed	23.83	0.10	22.92	0.04	17.57	0.02
Unemployed	24.10	0.38	22.76	-0.12	17.48	-0.08
European	25.11	1.38	22.88	0.00	17.53	-0.03
African	27.47	3.74	22.87	-0.01	17.47	-0.08
American	28.38	4.65	23.48	0.60	17.85	0.29
Asian	29.91	6.19	24.02	1.14	18.10	0.55
Oceania	20.97	-2.76	22.44	-0.45	17.35	-0.20
Stateless	22.40	-1.32	21.85	-1.03	17.07	-0.48

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

Exploring and understanding distributive environmental justice and air pollution relationships across different scales (European, national and local) is important as bringing this evidence to citizens can raise environmental consciousness in underserved communities. There is increasing evidence that indicates that people from low socio-economic background are more likely to suffer from exposure to air pollution which in turn creates health inequalities.

The emissions and concentrations variations coupled with individual and/or population demographics, practices and behaviours can result in disparities in exposure and related health risk and impacts. Thus greater understanding of the relationships between air pollution and socio-economic status can achieve greater public health / air quality management integration. This integration can target action in high-need areas, coordinating air pollution mitigation and health improvement interventions and connecting different policy areas.

For the ClairCity case study cities the following can be concluded:

- Bristol: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD). Spatially the area of most concern is the city centre with some ethnic groups suffering more exposure than the population mean.
- Amsterdam: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the proportion of low-income households. Spatially and across different demographics there are no notable variations, which may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the city population.
- Aveiro: There is no statistical correlation between emissions, concentrations and the proportion of low-income households. Spatially and across different demographics there are no notable variations, which may reflect the heterogeneous nature of the city population and the low concentrations across the region.
- Liguria: There is a slight, but not statistical, tendency for unemployment to be positively correlated with concentrations data, but not emissions. Spatially the area of most concern is the Genoa Port area and to the east of the port. Some ethnic groups suffered more exposure than the population mean.
- For Sosnowiec and Ljubljana no analysis could be undertaken at the sub-urban scale due to the lack of suitable demographic data.

Cities may have suitable data to derive meaningful conclusions but even in data-rich cities like Bristol and Amsterdam, the relationships and conclusions are often inconclusive. This may be due to a number of limitations related to the volume and quality of the spatial data; the analysis steps applied; and the stratification of the demographic data. Cities looking to undertake similar studies need to consider a number of process steps and overarching questions that go beyond understanding the distributional relationships and how that evidence can be used for targeted interventions. These include:

1. The suitability and availability of data at the right scales and the application of an appropriate analytical step.
2. Take care not to generalise the conclusions based on limited data and reflect on the suitability of the indicator of socio-economic status used.

3. The societal factors that help determine the exposure of different socio-economic groups.
4. How people can reduce their exposure and increase their resilience to air pollution.
5. The role that lifestyle factors and occupation may have in influencing the sensitivity and vulnerability and population groups.
6. The relative contribution of each pollutant and the cumulative impact of multiple air pollutants, multiple environmental stressors and wider determinants of public health.

6 References

- Bailey, J., Gerasopoulos, E., Rojas-Rueda, D. and Benmarhnia, T. (2019) Potential health and equity co-benefits related to the mitigation policies reducing air pollution from residential wood burning in Athens, Greece. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health - Part A Toxic/Hazardous Substances and Environmental Engineering* [online]. 54 (11), pp. 1144–1151. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10934529.2019.1629211> doi:10.1080/10934529.2019.1629211.
- Barnes, J., De Vito, L., Hayes, E., Guàrdia, N.B., Esteve, J.F. and Van Kamp, I. (2018) Qualitative assessment of links between exposure to noise and air pollution and socioeconomic status. *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*. 230 pp. 15–25. doi:10.2495/AIR180021.
- Barnes, J.H., Chatterton, T.J. and Longhurst, J.W.S. (2019) Emissions vs exposure: Increasing injustice from road traffic-related air pollution in the United Kingdom. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* [online]. 73 (June), pp. 56–66. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2019.05.012> doi:10.1016/j.trd.2019.05.012.
- Brook, R. and King, K. (2017) Updated Analysis of Air Pollution Exposure in London Report to Greater London Authority. *Aether*. (February), .
- Brunt, H., Barnes, J., Jones, S.J., Longhurst, J.W.S., Scally, G. and Hayes, E. (2017) Air pollution, deprivation and health: Understanding relationships to add value to local air quality management policy and practice in Wales, UK. *Journal of Public Health (United Kingdom)*. 39 (3), . doi:10.1093/pubmed/fdw084.
- Brunt, H., Barnes, J., Longhurst, J.W.S., Scally, G. and Hayes, E. (2018) Enhancing Local Air Quality Management to maximise public health integration, collaboration and impact in Wales, UK: A Delphi study. *Environmental Science and Policy*. 80 . doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2017.11.014.
- Brunt, H., Barnes, J., Longhurst, J.W.S., Scally, G. and Hayes, E. (2016) Local Air Quality Management policy and practice in the UK: The case for greater Public Health integration and engagement. *Environmental Science and Policy*. 58 . doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2016.01.009.
- COMEAP (2010) *The Mortality Effects of Long-Term Exposure to Particulate Air Pollution in the United Kingdom* [online].
- Deguen, S., Padilla, M. and Padilla, C. (2017) *Do Individual and Neighborhood Characteristics Influence Perceived Air Quality ?* doi:10.3390/ijerph14121559.
- European Environment Agency (2018) *Unequal exposure and unequal impacts — European Environment Agency*. Available from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/unequal-exposure-and-unequal-impacts/>.
- European Environmental Agency (2019) *Air quality in Europe — 2019 report — EEA Report No 10/2019*.
- Fairburn, J., Schüle, S.A., Dreger, S., Hilz, L.K. and Bolte, G. (2019) Social inequalities in exposure to ambient air pollution: A systematic review in the WHO European region. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 16 (17), . doi:10.3390/ijerph16173127.

- Fann, N., Nolte, C.G., Dolwick, P., Spero, T.L., Brown, A.C., Phillips, S. and Anenberg, S. (2015) The geographic distribution and economic value of climate change-related ozone health impacts in the United States in 2030. *Journal of the Air and Waste Management Association* [online]. 65 (5), pp. 570–580. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2014.996270>doi:10.1080/10962247.2014.996270.
- Flacke, J., Schüle, S.A., Köckler, H. and Bolte, G. (2016) Mapping environmental inequalities relevant for health for informing urban planning interventions—a case study in the city of Dortmund, Germany. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 13 (7), . doi:10.3390/ijerph13070711.
- Franck, U., Klimeczek, H.J. and Kindler, A. (2014) Social indicators are predictors of airborne outdoor exposures in Berlin. *Ecological Indicators* [online]. 36 pp. 582–593. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.08.023>doi:10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.08.023.
- García-muros, X., Burguillo, M., González-eguino, M., Romero-jordán, D., Burguillo, M. and González-eguino, M. (2017) *Local air pollution and global climate change taxes: a distributional analysis for the case of Spain*. 0568 . Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2016.1159951>doi:10.1080/09640568.2016.1159951.
- German, R., Williamson, T., May, K., King, K., Guardia, N.B., Horalek, J., Schovankova, J. and Schreiberova, M. (2018) *Analysis of Air Pollution and Social Deprivation*. (2018/7), .
- Gössling, S. (2016) Urban transport justice. *JTRG* [online]. 54 pp. 1–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2016.05.002>doi:10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2016.05.002.
- Landrigan, P.J., Fuller, R., Acosta, N.J.R., Adeyi, O., Arnold, R., Basu, N.N., Baldé, A.B., Bertollini, R., Fuster, V., Greenstone, M., Haines, A., Hanrahan, D., Hunter, D., Khare, M., et al. (2018) *The Lancet Commissions The Lancet Commission on pollution and health*. 391 . doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32345-0.
- Laurent, E. (2011) Issues in environmental justice within the European Union *Ecological Economics* 70 (11) p.pp. 1846–1853. doi:10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.06.025.
- Lipfert, F.W. (2004) Air pollution and poverty: Does the sword cut both ways? *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*. 58 (1), pp. 2–3. doi:10.1136/jech.58.1.2.
- Mitchell, G., Norman, P. and Mullin, K. (2015) *Who benefits from environmental policy? An environmental justice analysis of air quality change in Britain, 2001 – 2011* *Who benefits from environmental policy? An environmental justice analysis of air quality change in Britain, 2001 – 2011*.
- Nguyen, N.P. and Marshall, J.D. (2018) *Impact, efficiency, inequality, and injustice of urban air pollution: variability by emission location* *OPEN ACCESS Impact, efficiency, inequality, and injustice of urban air pollution: variability by emission location*.
- Olsen, J.R., Mitchell, R., Mutrie, N., Foley, L. and Ogilvie, D. (2017) Population levels of, and inequalities in, active travel: A national, cross-sectional study of adults in Scotland. *Preventive Medicine Reports* [online]. 8 (September), pp. 129–134. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2017.09.008>doi:10.1016/j.pmedr.2017.09.008.
- Openshaw, S. (1984) Ecological fallacies and the analysis of areal census data (UK, Italy). *Environment & Planning A*. 16 (1), pp. 17–31. doi:10.1068/a160017.
- Organization, W.H. (2014) Burden of disease from household air pollution for 2012. Summary of results. *World Health Organization* [online]. 35 (February), pp. 2012–2014. Available

from:

http://www.who.int/phe/health_topics/outdoorair/databases/FINAL_HAP_AAP_BoD_24_March2014.pdf.

- Paavola, J. (2017) *Health impacts of climate change and health and social inequalities in the UK*. 16 (Suppl 1), . doi:10.1186/s12940-017-0328-z.
- Padilla, C.M., Kihal-Talantikit, W., Vieira, V.M. and Deguen, S. (2016) City-specific spatiotemporal infant and neonatal mortality clusters: Links with socioeconomic and air pollution spatial patterns in France. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 13 (6), pp. 1–21. doi:10.3390/ijerph13060624.
- Poortinga, W., Dunstan, F.D. and Fone, D.L. (2008) *Neighbourhood deprivation and self-rated health : The role of perceptions of the neighbourhood and of housing problems*. 14 pp. 562–575. doi:10.1016/j.healthplace.2007.10.003.
- Rawls, J. (1993) *Political liberalism*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Richardson, E.A., Pearce, J., Tunstall, H., Mitchell, R. and Shortt, N.K. (2013) Particulate air pollution and health inequalities: A Europe-wide ecological analysis. *International Journal of Health Geographics* [online]. 12 (1), pp. 1. Available from: International Journal of Health Geographicsdoi:10.1186/1476-072X-12-34.
- Shrestha, R., Flacke, J., Martinez, J. and Maarseveen, M. Van (2016) *Environmental Health Related Socio-Spatial Inequalities : Identifying “ Hotspots ” of Environmental Burdens and Social Vulnerability*. doi:10.3390/ijerph13070691.
- Silva, C.D.S. and Panagopoulos, T. (2018) *Environmental Justice in Accessibility to Green*. doi:10.3390/land7040134.
- Walker, G. (2012) *Environmental justice: Concepts, Evidence and Politics*. Oxon: Routledge.

7 Annex 1: Data Sources

Table 9: Municipality boundary data and socio-economic data sources

City	Administrative boundary data	Source	Deprivation data	Source
Bristol	Lower Layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs)	https://data.gov.uk/dataset/fa883558-22fb-4a1a-8529-cffdee47d500/lower-layer-super-output-area-lsoa-boundaries	Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) 2019	http://data-communities.opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/indices-of-multiple-deprivation-imd-2019
Amsterdam	wijk- en buurtkaarten (2016) (buurt_2016) [neighborhood and neighborhood maps (2016)] (surrounding area) geojson (central area)	https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regionaal/geografische-data/wijk-en-buurtkaart-2016 https://maps.amsterdam.nl/open_geodata/?k=198	Income per household (low/medium/high) (adam_population_hh.csv)	ClairCity data portal (PBL)
Aveiro	BGRI11	Census data_Baixo Vouga (University of Aveiro)	unemployment/ data (N_IND_R_16)	Census data_Baixo Vouga (University of Aveiro)
Liguria	Genova_sezcens_D3_region (census sections)	liguria_sezcens_d3_shapefiles (ClairCity data portal - PBL)	P62; Resident population - total of 15 years and most unemployed seeking new employment	https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/104317
Ljubljana	Naselja_intersect_grid_region (Settlements)	ClairCity data portal (PBL)	Population by activity status, settlements, Slovenia, 2002 Census ¹¹	https://www.stat.si/popis2002/si/rezultati_naselja_prebivalstvo.asp?crka=L
Sosnowiec	Sosnowiec_Gminy (commune)	ClairCity data portal (PBL)	Population and housing census ¹²	https://geo.stat.gov.pl/en/

¹¹ No deprivation data or equivalent available at the settlement scale in Ljubljana

¹² No deprivation data or equivalent available at the commune scale in Sosnowiec

Table 10: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Bristol (n = 437)

Description	Min	Max	Mean	Std Dev
Air Pollution Concentrations				
Annual Mean NO ₂ (µg/m ³)	9.4	48.6	24.5	8.0
Annual Mean PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	10.4	19.6	12.9	1.8
Annual Mean PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	7.0	16.7	9.2	1.8
Total Population				
Total Population	1035	2980	1614	282
Age (number of population)				
Total Population				
0-15	42	850	300	109
16-24	72	1637	224	175
25-44	161	1159	476	164
45-64	104	760	376	89
>65	23	586	238	104
Ethnic Group (number of population)				
White	295	2745	1425	273
Mixed / Multiple Ethic Groups	1	204	44	33
Asian / Asian British	2	561	69	84
Black / African / Caribbean / Black British	0	595	30	70
Other	0	102	11	14

Table 11: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Amsterdam (n = 612)

Description	Min	Max	Mean	Std Dev
Air Pollution Concentrations				
Annual Mean NO ₂ (µg/m ³)	13.0	46.8	26.5	6.8
Annual Mean PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	13.8	19.4	16.7	1.2
Annual Mean PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	8.7	13.9	11.1	1.4
Population (number of population)				
Total	1	6196	916	847
Male	1	3403	504	481
Female	1	2793	426	396
Income (number of houses)				
High Income Houses	1	1427	151	156
Medium Income Houses	1	2143	274	263
Low Income Houses	1	3783	512	481
Age (number of population)				
15-44	1	3313	465	442
45-64	1	2050	304	285
>64	1	1316	169	160
Nationality (number of population)				
Dutch	1	3765	529	500
Foreign	1	334	401	409

Table 12: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Aveiro region (n = 9111)

Description	Min	Max	Mean	Std Dev
Air Pollution Concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)				
Annual Mean NO ₂	4.1	57.7	12.2	4.8
Annual Mean PM ₁₀	0.2	16.7	11.9	0.7
Annual Mean PM _{2.5}	0.0	11.8	10.0	0.2
Population (number of population)				
Total	0	673	38.3	44.4
Male	0	333	18.3	21.1
Female	0	340	20.0	23.5
Age (number of population)				
0-14	0	128	5.2	7.6
15-24	0	195	6.7	8.9
25-64	0	382	21.3	26.2
>64	0	160	7.2	8.4
Work Status (number of population)				
Employed	0	325	16.5	21.3
Unemployed	0	227	14.1	15.2

Table 13: Descriptive statistics for air pollution concentrations, demographic data and indicators of socio-economic status for each spatial area in Liguria region (n = 3284)

Description	Min	Max	Mean	Std Dev
Air Pollution Concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)				
Annual Mean NO ₂	1.5	77.9	21.0	11.8
Annual Mean PM ₁₀	15.2	39.9	21.6	3.7
Annual Mean PM _{2.5}	13.7	26.9	16.9	1.9
Population (number of population)				
Total	0	917	166.3	158.6
Male	0	423	77.6	73.5
Female	0	704	88.7	85.8
Age (number of population)				
0-14	0	122	19.1	19.2
15-24	0	114	13.5	13.9
25-44	0	231	40.0	38.8
44-64	0	275	47.9	46.0
>64	0	528	45.8	47.7
Work Status (number of population)				
Employed	0	369	66.3	62.8
Unemployed	0	61	4.4	5.3
Nationality (number of population)				
European	0	79	3.7	6.1
African	0	123	1.7	5.2
American	0	162	5.8	13.0
Asian	0	54	1.5	4.2
Oceania	0	1	0.0	0.1
Stateless	0	1	0.0	0.0

8 Annex 2: Overview of the ClairCity Process

The ClairCity Project (www.claircity.eu) aims to substantially improve future air quality and carbon policies in European cities by initiating new modes of engaging citizens, stakeholders and policymakers. The latest social science thinking is applied to understand citizens' behaviour and source apportion air pollution emissions and concentrations, carbon emissions and health outcomes in order to attribute them not just by technology but by citizens' behaviour and daily activities. By putting people at the heart of both the problems and the solutions (primarily framed around transport and domestic energy use), ClairCity stimulates the public engagement necessary to tackle our challenging problems through the development of a range of citizen-led future scenario and policy packages. The four primary objectives of the ClairCity project are:

1. To put citizens' behaviour and activities at the heart of air quality and carbon management and policy making;
2. To develop a suite of innovative toolkits for enhanced quantification, engagement and impact evaluation;
3. To explore the integration of citizens' behaviour in relevant city policies and ensure that future city policies are reflective of citizens' visions for their future city; and
4. To raise awareness of environmental challenges and their solutions through proactive dissemination of the project outcomes.

The ClairCity process has three key process phases with a number of activities that work towards achieving the project aims and objectives. These three phases and related activities are briefly summarised here and illustrated below (Figure 15) to help the reader understand the flow of evidence and the positioning of the Environmental Justice Assessment within the wider ClairCity process. This process has been applied across all six ClairCity case study areas with some localisation and adaptation as required.

8.1.1.1 Phase 1: Establish the Baseline Evidence

The primary aim of Phase 1 is to understand and quantify the baseline status of air quality, carbon emissions and related public health in our cities. Phase 1 is achieved with the following main activities:

1. **Benchmarking behaviour:** Understanding the local demographic data and establishing the citizen practice-activity data to feed into the air quality models (WP3).
2. **Quantify the baseline:** Quantification of the baseline air quality emissions and concentrations, carbon emissions and public health impacts in our city (WP5).
3. **Assessment of Policy:** Collation and analysis of current policies (local, regional, national and EU) that influence the city (WP6).

8.1.1.2 Phase 2: Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement & Co-creation of Scenarios

Phase 2 has three key aims: (1) understand citizens' current behaviours, practices and activities, (2) enable citizens and stakeholder to co-create and visualise their low carbon, clean air, future city and (3) raise awareness of the environmental challenges and their solutions. Phase 2 utilised evidence from Phase 1 to help frame and inform the engagement activities. Phase 2 is achieved with the following main activities:

Citizen and stakeholder engagement & co-creation

1. The ClairCity Delphi method uses citizens as local experts to generate qualitative evidence of their entrenched behaviours and what enabling interventions would allow them to act and behave differently in future (WP4).
2. The Mutual Learning Workshop brings citizens and stakeholders together to debate the challenges facing the city and co-create policy interventions for cleaner, healthier futures (WP4).
3. The ClairCity Skylines Game 'crowd-sources' the public perceptions and public acceptability of difference policy interventions (WP4).
4. Citizens and stakeholders come together in a Stakeholder Dialogue Workshop to review and debate the Delphi, Mutual Learning Workshop and ClairCity Skylines evidence and co-create scenarios for a low carbon, clean air, health futures (WP4 and WP7).
5. The scenarios generated in the Stakeholder Dialogue Workshop go through a rapid quantification step (WP5) and are then returned to the local citizens/stakeholders to discuss in a Policy Workshop (WP6) and to agree a single Unified Policy Scenario (WP7).

Public Engagement & Awareness: Additional awareness raising activities are also implemented across the project in each city (WP4). These include:

1. The GreenAnt App which allows citizens to become citizen scientists and monitor their transport activities, emission generation and exposure using mobile GPS data.
2. The School Competition: My City, My School, My Home engages young people in the air quality, carbon and public health debate utilising an online platform for the students to select the interventions that influence their housing, transport and use of resources in order to be able to design tools for change towards smart consumption, reduced emissions and healthy lifestyles.
3. Learning from the elderly filming activity engages the older, potentially vulnerable, community to talk about the changes in their city, their personal mobility and the steps they take to minimise their exposure.
4. The City Day: Discovering my City helps disseminate the final project results and provide healthy and smart tips to promote non-motorised mobility of citizens by highlighting availability and benefits of walking and cycling routes in the city.

8.1.1.3 Phase 3: Quantified Policy Package & Knowledge Exchange

The primary aim of the final Phase 3 is to collate the evidence and lessons learned from Phase 1 and Phase 2 to generate a quantified, bespoke, citizen-led and citizen-inclusive policy package for each city. Phase 3 is achieved with the following main activities:

1. **Knowledge Exchange:** Collation of transferrable lessons and steps for better practice based on the experiences of the ClairCity project to inform other environmental and public health practitioners (WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7).
2. **Impact Assessment:** Rapid quantification of the broad baseline evidence, scenarios generated in the Stakeholder Dialogue Workshop (WP4) and detailed impact assessment of the final Unified Policy Scenario generated in the Policy Workshop (WP6). This quantification includes consideration of source apportionment by

behaviour or purpose; air quality emissions and concentrations, carbon emissions, air pollution related health impact and interventions cost analysis (WP5). The Environmental Justice Assessment was undertaken using the outputs of the city modelling.

3. **Policy Package:** Development of a bespoke Policy Package for each city drawing together the findings from across the whole project (WP7).

Figure 15: ClairCity process including key phases and activities (Environmental Justice Assessment highlighted in red box)